

ANALYSIS OF THE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF ROAD CONSTRUCTION ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: Currently, the construction of highways is one of the urgent problems. There is a need to introduce the principles of public-private partnership in the field of design, construction, reconstruction and perfect maintenance of public highways and regional highways. Based on this point of view, in the article, the author describes the analysis of structural elements of the efficiency of road construction entrepreneurship based on valid evidence.

Key words: investment, employment, infrastructure, automobile, road construction, enterprise, cost, efficiency, innovation, human capital, ecology, World Bank, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, Asian Development Bank, Islamic Development Bank, Saudi Development Fund, Kuwait Arab Economic Development Fund.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda avtomobil yo'llarini qurish dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib kelmoqda. Umumiy foydalanishdagi avtomobil yo'llarini va hududiy avtomobil yo'llarini loyihalash, qurish, rekonstruksiya qilish va mukammal ta'mirlash sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik tamoyillarini joriy etishga zaruriyat etilmoqda. Shu nuqtai-nazardan kelib chiqib muallif maqolada avtomobil yo'l qurilishi tadbirkorligi samaradorligi tarkibiy elementlarining tahlili asosli

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya, bandlik, infratuzilma, avtomobil, yo'l qurilishi, korxonalar, xarajat, samaradorlik, innovatsiya, inson kapitali, ekologiya, Jahon banki, Yevropa tiklanish va taraqqiyot banki, Osiyo taraqqiyot banki, Islom taraqqiyot banki, Saudiya taraqqiyot jamg'armasi, Quvayt arab iqtisodiy taraqqiyot jamg'armasi.

Аннотация: В настоящее время строительство автомобильных дорог является одной из актуальных проблем. Необходимо внедрение принципов государственно-частного партнерства в сфере проектирования, строительства, реконструкции и безупречного содержания автомобильных дорог общего пользования и региональных автодорог. Исходя из этой точки зрения, в статье автор на основе достоверных данных описывает анализ структурных элементов эффективности дорожно-строительного предпринимательства.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, занятость, инфраструктура, автомобиль, дорожное строительство, предприятие, стоимость, эффективность, инновации, человеческий капитал, экология, Всемирный банк, Европейский банк реконструкции и развития, Азиатский банк развития, Исламский банк развития, Саудовское развитие. Фонд, Кувейтский арабский фонд экономического развития.

Introduction. Taking into account the geographical location of the republic, the development of a modern road network is a priority task in increasing the competitiveness of our country's economy, developing the republic's transport potential, and expanding export opportunities. At the same time, projects in the field of road construction are being successfully implemented in collaboration with international financial institutions such as the World Bank, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the Asian Development Bank, the Islamic Development Bank, the Saudi Development Fund, and the Kuwait Fund for Arab Economic Development.

Main part. The relationship between factors affecting the efficiency of road construction and the efficiency of business can be expressed as in Figure 1. This figure shows the relationship between the factors affecting the efficiency of a road construction enterprise and the results resulting from achieving efficiency. Without denying the impact of the 6 sub-indices of the Road Construction Enterprise Productivity Index (LPI) calculated by the World Bank on the efficiency of the road construction enterprise, we have separately identified the factors affecting this type of road construction enterprise. Now let's dwell on

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Infrastructure is a factor that is also reflected in the sub-indicators of the overall road construction enterprise performance index. Infrastructure is a sub-index of the World Bank's Road Construction Enterprise Performance Index that

og of cargo carriers, aiming to further improve the state of cargo transportation infrastructure. This catalog will include both local and international carriers and will reflect their technical and economic indicators. Based on the idea of

issue today to turn the "7 R" rule of road construction enterprises, which we mentioned above, into a "Golden Rule" by including this very harm reduction.

The results to be achieved as a result of environmentally friendly supply chain management are "Economic growth" and "Environmental sustainability".

n entrepreneurship today, we encounter the trilemma "Innovation" - "efficiency of road construction" - "Environmental condition".

In order to determine the opinion of the road construction enterprise in our country in taking a step towards a Green economy, we included the question “Can you abandon environmentally harmful means in your activities when transitioning to a green economy?” in our questionnaire titled “Determining the effectiveness of the road construction enterprise” . To this question, 7.1% of the

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